

Effect of Dioxane and Ethanol on the Rate of Coagulation of Thorium Oxide Sol

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The effects of addition of dioxane and ethanol on the rate of coagulation of thorium oxide sol by KCl have been studied by measurements of turbidity at certain intervals of time. It has been found that as the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased by the addition of any one of the aforesaid organic liquids, the time taken to attain a particular turbidity becomes shorter. If D is the dielectric constant of the medium and t the experimentally measured time to attain a certain turbidity then $\log t$ is found to be proportional to $\log D$.

FOR high concentration of an organic solvent or for a sol in non-aqueous medium the dielectric constant is likely to play an important role in determining the stability. This follows from the equation for flocculation values of mono-, di-, and trivalent counter ions in which it enters in the third power¹. From the data of Weiser and Mack² on HgS and of Mackor³ on Ag I sols, the above stated third power prediction has been qualitatively verified. Furthermore, from the experimental results of several authors^{4,5,6} it may be concluded that most of the hydrophobic sols are generally sensitized to the action of univalent counter ions by the addition of a non-ionic substance. In this paper the results of investigation on the effects of dioxane and ethanol on the rate of coagulation of KCl will be recorded.

Experimental

The thorium oxide sol has been prepared by Muller's⁷ method with slight modification⁸. The sol is filtered through Corning fine glass filter (16 microns) in order to free it from coarse particles and any optical impurities which it may contain. The sol thus obtained is almost transparent with a bluish tinge and is positively charged. The composition of the sol is 2.5 g per cent and its specific conductance at 25° is 1.27×10^{-4} mho cm^{-1} and pH 3.2. The ζ potential of the unfiltered sol has been found by the micro cataphoretic method to be 43.1 m. v.

A definite volume of the sol has been used and the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte KCl is so adjusted that the rate of aggregation is slow. The final concentration of the electrolyte has been maintained at 2.98×10^{-2} M. Different volumes of purified dioxane and ethanol have been used to vary the dielectric constant of the medium. Molecular ratios of dioxane-water mixtures thus prepared are 0.0526, 0.0702 and 0.0902 and those of ethanol-water are 0.077, 0.1036 and 0.1762. The dielectric constants of the mixtures found from standard tables are 59.7, 55.4, 51.0 and 64.0, 62.5 and 59.0 respectively at 25°.

Turbidity measurements have been carried out with a Brice-Phoenix universal light scattering instrument. Apparent turbidity has been corrected by multiplying with the correction factor^{9,10}. Light of wavelength 546nm has been used. The intensity of scattered light has been measured at different angles in the circular scale. Correction for refractive indices have also been made. The change in turbidity of the sol with time in both the cases, has been noted just after mixing with electrolyte.

Results

In the Figures 1 and 2 are shown the changes of turbidity with time. It is apparent that in both the cases the time required to attain a certain turbidity changes as the composition of the mixture is changed. We no consider the arbitrary points where the turbidities are 0.06 and 0.52 for dioxane-water and 0.07 for ethanol-water mixtures. They are recorded in the Tables 1 to 3.

Fig. 1. Mixtures of dioxane and water.
○ Molecular Ratio of dioxane to water = 0.0526
● " " " " = 0.0702
◐ " " " " = 0.0902

Fig. 2. Mixtures of ethanol and water.
 ○ Molecular Ratio of alcohol to water = 0.077
 ● " " " " " " = 0.1036
 ● " " " " " " = 0.1762

A plot of $\log t$ against $\log D$ is shown in the figures 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. Mixtures of dioxane and water.
 t = Time in minutes
 D = Dielectric constant
 ○ Turbidity = 0.062
 ● " " = 0.060

Discussion

According to Reerink¹¹ and Verwey and Overbeek¹² the stability ratio, W , defined as the ratio of the limiting rate of rapid congulation to the rate of slow coagulation can be related to the dielectric constant, D , under considerations in which the temperature and the concentration of the added electrolyte (symmetrical) are maintained constant and the surface potential ψ_0 is high, by an equation of the following type :

$$\log W = -k_1 + k_2 \log D \quad \dots (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are constants.

Again it follows from definition that

$$W = \frac{t}{T} \quad \dots \quad \dots (2)$$

where t is the time required to attain a certain stage of turbidity when the rate of coagulation is slow and T a constant representing the characteristic time of rapid coagulation.

Therefore, under the conditions mentions above

$$\log t \propto \log D. \quad \dots (3)$$

From an examination of the figures 1 and 2 it appears that as the dielectric constant of the medium decreases the time taken to attain a particular turbidity becomes smaller. It may, therefore, be concluded that for the same electrolyte concentration the gradual addition of dioxane or ethanol accelerates the rate of coagulation.

Fig. 4. Mixtures of ethanol and water.
 t = Time in minutes
 D = Dielectric constant
 ○ Turbidity = 0.07

In Figures 3 and 4 $\log t$ has been plotted against $\log D$. It will be noticed that the plot is linear within the limited range of D investigated and is thus in agreement with equation (3).

TABLE 1—DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE. TURBIDITY 0.06

Molecular ratio of dioxane to water	Dielectric constant, D	Log D	Time in minutes, t	log t
0.0526	59.7	1.7760	140	2.1461
0.0792	55.4	1.7435	47	1.6721
0.0902	51.0	1.7076	15	1.1761

TABLE 2—DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE. TURBIDITY 0.062

Molecular ratio of dioxane to water	Dielectric constant, D	Log D	Time in minutes, t	log t
0.0526	59.7	1.7760	169.00	2.2279
0.0702	55.4	1.7435	62.50	1.7959
0.0902	51.0	1.7076	18	1.2553

TABLE 3—ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE. TURBIDITY 0.07

Molecular ratio of ethanol to water	Dielectric constant, D	Log D	Time in minutes, t	log t
0.077	64.0	1.8062	282	2.4502
0.1036	62.5	1.7959	154	2.1875
0.1762	59	1.7709	27	1.4314

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